

ROLE, NATURE AND SCOPE OF TRANSLATION IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract In the 21st century the role of translation has become even more significant. Translation studies are not only an interesting but a challenging job also it is highly skillful action and profession in the twenty-first century. Translation practice is an intercultural activity through languages, with adequate sensitivity and knowledge of the cultures of both the languages, the translator becomes a mediator who creates the scope and means to transfer the meaning and experience of the original text into another language.

Key words: Translation studies, language, scope, role, nature, and culture of translation.

The English word translation derives from the latin word ‘translatio’ which comes from trans, across ferre ‘to carry’ or to bring (latio in turn coming from latus) Thus, translatio is ‘a carrying across’ or ‘a bringing across’. Translation has emerged and flourished as a new field with a lot of ideas springing from anthropology, philosophy, literature, linguistics, literary studies, lexicology, semiotics and many other fields. Both written and spoken translation have played a crucial role in the inter-human communication throughout history. The term ‘translation studies’ was coined by the Amsterdam-based American scholar James S. Holmes in his paper ‘The name and nature of translation studies’, this is considered as a foundational text. The Ancient Greek term is ‘metaphrasis (to speak across) and this gives is the term ‘metaphrase’. this distinction has laid at the heart of the theory of translation throughout its history: Cicero and Horace employed it in the seventeenth century and it still exists today in the discussion around ‘fidelity versus transparency’ or

‘formal equivalence versus dynamic equivalence’. The first known translations are those of the Sumerian epic Gilgamesh into Asian languages from the second millennium BC.

Translation is a production process of conveying meaning and information underlying in the source language into target language with the help of linguistic and cultural convenience. The scope of translation is a bright and beautiful in the coming years because it is the only medium through different people come to know different works. Today many people think that anyone who knows more than one language can become a translator or interpreter. But it is only a half-truth because a good translator must have good background knowledge of both language, subject knowledge, social, and cultural competence and apart from it he/she need advanced language skills for the medium of communication. The fact that we are able to produce equivalent in English for every word does not mean that we can give an adequate translation of the text. We can express their thought in a manner that is not only parallel to the original text, but also acceptable to the target language. A good translation shows a “spontaneous and creative process of journey of a theme and a meta theme from one linguistic framework to another.” We need to be faithful and loyal to the original text while act of translation and it is necessary to focus more on ideas and concepts than its surface meaning of the text.

We are going to mention Jacobson’s threefold of translation which he proposed in his epoch-making essay ‘On the Linguistic aspects of Translation’

(a) **Intralingual translation**, or ‘rewarding’ – an interpretation of verbal signs by means of the other signs of the same language.

(b) **Interlingual translation**, or translation proper’– an interpretation of Verbal signs by means of some other languages.

(c) **Intersemiotic translation**, or ‘transmutation’- an interpretation of verbal signs by means of signs of non-verbal sign system.

There are two major ways of translation: *literary* and *machine translation* where theoretician initiates in both means. There is a big gap between literary and machine translation. *Machine translation* is a sub-field of computational linguistics

that investigates the use of software to translate a text or speech in a very useful in the live programme or some international discussion. The arrival of newer centers of language suggests that there is no dearth of economic opportunities for aspiring to take up translation or interpretation as a full time profession in language like English, Hindi, Chinese, Japanese, Arabic, Russian etc.

The translator of a literary text will have to bridge the gap small or large between cultures. The main problem of the translator is how to comply with cultural issues i.e. which issues to take priority: the cultural aspect of target language community or perhaps a combination between the two.

According to French humanist Etienne Dolet in 1540 established five principles for translators such as follows:

- a) The translator must fully understand the sense and meaning of the original author.
- b) The translator should have a perfect knowledge of both the Source Language and Target Language.
- c) The translator should avoid word for word renderings.
- d) The translator should choose and order words appropriately to produce the correct tone.
- e) The translator should use forms of speech in common use.

The translation of a literary text become a transaction not between two languages, but rather a more complex negotiation between two cultures of any two languages. Every text holds multiple dynamic significance within its deep linguistic and compositional structure. On close reading one might find a literary text enlightening one further that its stated purpose or reveling hidden context.

Conclusion

In this way, I would like to conclude my article that Translation is an essential in the study of any literature. In brief, English language has become a backbone language so is the translation in the 21st century. As English is for all so “translation is for all.” To be a translator, knowing the two languages is not enough. The translator serves as a mediator of between cultures and systematizes and generalizes

the process of translation. Finally, I would like to say, India is paradise for translator and translation has a great scope in our country.

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